

The Operation Strategy and Public Relations Trend for Public Relations Strategies Development in Thailand

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Abstract—The purpose of this study is to analyze the operation strategy strategies and public relations trend for public relations strategies development in public television station in Thailand. This study is a qualitative approach by indent interview from the 6 key informants that are managers of Voice TV and Thairath TV Channel. The results showed that both TV stations have to do research before making a release on the operation strategy policy such as a slogan, segmentation, integrated marketing communication and PR activity and also in term of Public Relations trend are including online media, online content and online training before opening the station and start promoting. By the way, we found the PR strategy for both TV station should be including application on mobile, online content, CRM activity, online banner, special event, and brand ambassador in order to bring a very reliable way.

Keywords—Operation strategy, public relations trend, public relations strategies development, online banner.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN Thailand, the development of new forms of television transmission and broadcast from old analog to new digital-quality video and audio channels and sharper than the original system (the analog). The agency take responsibilities include broadcasting commission on TV and telecoms. The National Telecommunications Commission or NTC, which stands on behalf of government representative to extended digital signal transmission channel frequency and modify signaling techniques ground systems. (Terrestrial) from the analog system to a digital system, that will enhance the transmission of signals to be clearer and allow more channels to deliver more particular signaling high definition (High-Definition) or HD. The TV channels are increasingly giving viewers the option of watching more channels have been assigned a number of digital television channels, consisting initially of 48 channels from the beginning from the opening of a public service channel for 12-channel service type business group of 24 national channels [2] to change the format of the broadcast TV. In this cause, the audience was the result in some confusion and the watcher has switched the channel to expand and add to the cause of expansion, new stations at many stations TV channels exist and new fields that happened [1].

In terms of controversy audience, the competition environment within among of digital TV and analog TV. PR is considered as an important tool to help all of them to create awareness and offering different and unique in their channels

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to the viewers as communication tools. That why the publicity this was to strengthen relations and understanding between the institutions with the audience, doing the research. See the tender for key aspects of public relations and look for strategies for implementation of digital television. Since it is a new thing in Thailand and that is what the audience is not familiar, and in some niche content producers have difficulties in communication that is neutral, since the channel partners who have been involved in national politics [3].

The researchers studied the operation strategies and trends in public relations of digital TV to operates and created awareness for replacing or distract the audience from traditional television to make TV viewing patterns and understand how new digital TV is working. This research aims to find strategies, publicity, and public relations trends of digital television, which is a type of journalism organization. The study compared two TV stations broadcast Voice TV is a new organization copyright set up to broadcast TV. This is an organization with a large media and the print media industry as the "Thairath newspaper" support existing ones to learn about the strategies, operations, and prospects of relations between the two channels that have the same or different in any aspect of the objectives of the study are summarized as follows [2].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Operations Strategy Concept

The operations strategy constructs are used in this research: strategic consensus (managerial consensus within business units on business strategy), manufacturing task consensus (managerial consensus within business units on manufacturing strategy), product-process alignment (the "correct" alignment of product life cycle stage and production process type), the use of advanced TV Digital systems and technologies, and TV Digital/operational performance [4].

A major theme of the literature on operations strategy is that consensus on general strategic direction and on manufacturing task emphasis must exist between business-level strategic planners and functional-level TV Digital managers for effective business unit performance to consistently occur. A well-developed TV Digital strategy is defined as an operational strategy (pursuit of manufacturing task objectives) that is consistent with the business unit's general strategic direction for the focal. It is the responsibility of the manufacturing manager to develop a manufacturing strategy that supports the business unit strategy. An effective

manufacturing strategy is not necessarily one that promises maximum operating efficiency. Rather, it is an operational strategy designed to fit the specific needs of the strategic business unit, i.e. a functional plan that seeks consistency between manufacturing task emphasis and the type of competitive advantage being sought by the strategic business unit [5]. Operations strategy scholars postulate that effective business unit performance results in no small part from a coordinated and consistent manufacturing strategy that affects a close match between production system objectives (manufacturing task performance objectives) and capabilities and the demands of the marketplace, as reflected in the business unit strategy.

The manufacturing function should be viewed as a powerful competitive weapon or strategic tool. Ideally, the manufacturing function will properly support the business level strategy and avoid a mismatch between general strategic objectives and manufacturing task objectives for the focal product. Scholars warn that a manufacturing business unit will have a decreased competitive advantage within its industry if it fails to develop a coordinated and supportive operations strategy [6]. Such an ideal synchronization of manufacturing strategy and business strategy, however, may not be the norm among business units engaged in manufacturing. Importantly, for this state to occur, a common understanding of the purpose and task direction must exist among business-level strategic planners and manufacturing managers. A unifying strategy has required a vision that manufacturing managers clearly understand and implement. All too often this shared understanding or consensus does not occur. For example, found evidence of a rapid hierarchical decline in strategic awareness within organizations. Significant declines in strategic awareness were exhibited by second-level executives [7].

B. Public Relations Strategies

A strategy is an observable phenomenon that refers to a behavioral sequence enacted in pursuit of some goal or objective. Communication strategies are messages enacted to accomplish specific goals relevant to specific communication situations. Thus, strategies are situational constructs. Public relations behavior in organizations is enacted through communication strategies designed to achieve organizational goals. Communication strategies are manifest in the form of messages that serve as inputs to target audiences located in the environment [4]. This manifestation is a functional result of the communication process—a process defined by encoding and delivery of messages through the analysis of symbols that symbols are observable, tangible parts of the communication process. Public relations communication consists of one or more symbols encoded as a message by an organization and decoded by public. In order for communication to be effective, symbols or symbol systems must be shared or at least understood by both source and receiver in the communication process. As socially constructed objects that take physical form and have predictable effects, symbols may

be viewed as organizational resources. Organizations expand other types of resources to develop and use symbolic resources in order to accomplish organizational goals [8].

It is possible to analyze messages as symbolic communication that contains unique physical, psychological, and social properties. “Physically, messages are tangible stimuli that can be perceived. Psychologically, meanings attributed to messages by receivers can be specified. Socially, significant others influence individual message evaluation processes” [9]. The used these concepts to develop a matrix for the analysis of public relations messages as symbolic communication. The top of the matrix reflects increasing levels of abstraction of the audience in terms of message effects and message processing. At the first level, messages are seen as physical objects to be apprehended and processed by individuals. At the second level, messages are seen as objects to be understood by individuals, so their psychological impact is considered. At the third level, the impact of social processes on symbol effects is considered [10].

The left side of the matrix consists of three general concepts—content, structure and function that reflect assumptions about the characteristics of messages. Although these concepts are present at every point in the communication process, they are aspects of symbolic messages that can be viewed independently. As a result, they can be recognized and understood without knowing the motive or the characteristics of the source of the message.

Content refers to the manifest characteristics of messages. Structure refers to the distribution and frequency of communication elements within a particular level of analysis. Function references the audience and reflects assumptions about message effects and identified six functions of messages at the psychological level that reflect public relations strategies used by organizations when communicating with publics. These functions represent the goals of public relations in terms of the impact messages have on audiences and the meanings audiences attribute to messages. The six functions are; facilitate, inform, persuade, coerce, bargain, and solve problems [4].

This study will analyze the strategies and operations of running the release of two digital television station and study the trend of public relations organization of two digital television stations.

III.METHODOLOGY

This research is qualitative research using in-depth interviews to collect the data with the purposive sampling. There is a connection with public relations and disseminating information on the scope of the study sample in this study is the chief executive officer of the authority to decide whether or television station who was involved in communication and public relations, direct marketing of the station by storing data with in-depth interviews (In-depth Interview). The key informant interviews of a private placement (Purposive Sampling), including its chief executive officer and owner of a

part of the public relations and communications the list of stations below [7].

To approach with consumers or receivers in a new era and the researcher notes and record the issues of interest which, apart from the questions in the interview prepared with a tape recorder to use it for gathering information from interviews along with the correct information intended to be exhaustive as to study synthesizing results correctly and data analysis methods. Data from the interviews were transcribed, and separate issue from the question then analyze each issue in a series of questions and ideas center discussed the implementation process releases into four phases [6]:

1. It is the first step of the public relations working these finding factual information about issues that institution are facing to mark the beginning of the release.
2. Planning - Decision the process of planning and that decision activity and strategies to be used in any publicity or public relations work to resolve the problems facing the institution.
3. Communication is the process of compliance with the plan in step 2 using the tools, techniques, and strategies to communicate the news [9].
4. Evaluation as a final step of the PR aims to track how public relations have done so much good.

Including ideas about publicity of Marston mentioned by the public relations activities of the four major events. This is an element in the process, including public relations and presents information by writing descriptive analysis with important issues about implementation strategies, public relations and discussed at the end [8].

IV. FINDINGS

In this article, we will put forward its findings by research objectives 1 and 2 offer, which was the subject of the strategies of public relations and trends in the public relations by researchers share presentations together to each of the two stations in question are consistent with the objectives of the research [6].

A. The Implementation of Strategies to Promote the Work of Two Digital Television Stations

The analysis of documents and interviews found that each of the data collected has been targeting and clear stance on the channel and the public through the media and the various public can check with the agency responsible for promoting separate from other parts of the show has inadequate information [10].

1. Thai Rath TV is a name that slogan "I truly understand," then put the target audience the general public and in the first part aims to create awareness, communication, since both channels have emerged for the first time in Thailand, thus making communication easy to understand.
2. Voice TV different from the Thai Rath TV audience by choosing only one is working, a new era, and the focus on using the tagline of the channel. "Think smart, intelligent life."

3. Thai Rath TV support a variety of tools is available as a traditional book and media partners over the hands, while the voice TVs use fewer media because the media all need to buy a low budget.
4. Thai Rath TV does the marketing communications, public relations department, but not directly work together with the audience care workers or members of the work items. Under the holding company Trend VG 3 Limited and the company has been doing publicity outside to help in the campaign is the company Poly Plus. Ltd., a company, affiliated.
5. The voice TV is operated by the Public Relations will work with friendly personnel within the organization. The cooperative relations activities planned in conjunction department of marketing and public relations department, and it has hired an outside public relations firm to help the public unless there is a big event, it employed only regarding the Event marketing just to help recipients in the News [4].

Both the stations have to do research before making a release by the Thai Rath TV. A small research group initially before the station opened and Voice TV is researching the behavior of the target before the opening of the station and at the start of data collection in order to promote strategic planning work. Thai Rath TV by using existing information in the media business with a focus group a little while Voice TV -focus on researching consumer than by prior research, public relations and research after the release. Additionally, because the only major group to communicate clearly and there is not much communication budget, and the research results show that the station has selected the city that is the main target group that has the power to tell the receiver social credibility [10].

B. Trends in Public Relations Organization of Two Digital Television Station

The trend of public relations, The Thai Rath TV will be the featured content and appropriate in each area due to the publicity that will meet the audience and makes people more open and engaging content to watch other channels in the next sequence [9].

Public relations trends in both fields have been using online channels with the relations activities and special events in various formats to engage with their target audience further. PR Both stations also agreed that when the watch and enjoy the show's content, the goal is to share the content of such other recipients as a tool to promote a kind of way station. And they will not invest on such thing, but viewers are forwarded within your network and get back to the station or organization as well. The consumer or audience today has changed watching television through online rather than watching the television in the home. This has a dramatic effect on the ratings that led to the planning of public relations and content management strategies of digital television stations in the next generation [10]. The summary tends to use the

publicity of both stations can be further subdivided into the following topics.

- o TV Station Thai Rath TV
- 1. Application on Mobile (Creating apps function of the Thai Rath TV.)
- 2. Content online (Main navigation list on the Web site YouTube to watch back.)
- 3. CAI (Customer activity increased.)
- 4. Direct content to Target (Led a distinguished list of public channels to match the audience directly.)
- o Voice TV station
- 1. Banner online (The banner on the Facebook. People press Likes: Currently, the press likes more than 1, 000 000 people.)
- 2. Shot cut content Online (Content channels were shortened and taken to the station and online media to promote people to visit.)
- 3. Special Event (Special events such as concerts and workshops.)
- 4. Bran Ambassador (The host of the station building as a brand ambassador) [4].

V. DISCUSSION

To change the format of TV broadcasting from analog to digital in the view of the target audience was found the result in some confusion. Due to watching the channel has switched to the extended and expanded in this way causes expansion the new stations with several stations and for the channel Voice TV, they are limited in terms of the politics support the government of Thaksin Shinawatra. The results showed that both stations (Voice TV and Thai Rath TV) are ready to release it before it on aired from April since 2557. The study revealed the interesting issue of the two stations since entering the digital TV era it just happens to be the first because, in the past, Thailand had a 5-6 TV channels only but when it comes to digital TV which includes 24 channels simultaneously at one time, thus causing confusion. The broadcast channel number in each box are not synchronized because difficulties in communication and to create awareness in the first period. The interviews revealed that the government has to contribute of strategic planning and public relations tool that both stations are using tools that are based on the theories of public relations is to consider the use of tools from:

1. Target,
2. Publicity purposes,
3. A number of personnel resources and budgets [5].

VI. RECOMMENDATION AND FUTURE STUDIES

Researchers have suggested being useful for those who are interested in researching and may be educational research to check the results of the research were presented as follows.

1. Carefully study the effectiveness of public relations to achievement or measurement of communication tools to influence consumer perception and promote efficiency and effectiveness.

2. Learn more about the strategies and trends in public relations problem of digital TV in other fields. To lead the development of public relations tools in line with the new generation has to go [8].

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